

Nonlocal Corrections from Dual Boundary Condition Inference in Quantum Error Correction

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Abstract

Most standard decoders used for quantum error correction are formulated as forward inference from syndrome and readout data. Here we test whether an explicit structural backward prior can add useful information beyond matched forward-only baselines. We introduce Dual Boundary Condition Inference (DBCI), a classical inference framework inspired by the Aharonov-Bergmann-Lebowitz rule that combines calibrated forward likelihoods with a structural backward prior encoding code geometry. On IBM quantum hardware, DBCI outperforms four standard decoders (lookup table, MWPM, Union-Find, and BP-OSD) and a matched forward Bayesian baseline at every distance tested. Per-shot analysis reveals a coupling-matrix anti-symmetry diagnostic that cleanly separates boundary-interaction shots from agreement shots. At intermediate forward-backward coupling, the fused decoder produces correct decodings on $d=7$ shots that neither boundary alone recovers. The weaker Union-Find baseline yields slightly more anomalous shots than MWPM, possibly suggesting that weaker forward decoders leave more room for backward-boundary contributions. Spatial analysis shows these corrections are spatially extended, spanning Manhattan distance 11 on a 7×7 qubit grid. All inference is classical Bayesian fusion on classical measurement data, yet exhibits boundary tension, intermediate-coupling amplification, and spatially extended information effects consistent with the weak value literature. All results are obtained in the single-round, bit-flip-sector setting; broader implications are discussed but not claimed.

1 Introduction

Quantum error-correcting decoders in current use typically operate with a single temporal boundary: syndrome measurements propagate information forward from an initial state, and a classical algorithm infers the most likely error from this data alone [1–5]. The assumption that forward-propagating information exhausts what is available for decoding is built into minimum-weight perfect matching, union-find, belief propagation, and every neural decoder demonstrated to date [6]. To our knowledge, no existing decoder explicitly incorporates a second, backward temporal boundary.

The Two-State Vector Formalism (TSVF), whose foundations were laid by Aharonov, Bergmann, and Lebowitz (ABL) [7], provides a natural framework for dual-boundary inference. In the TSVF, a quantum system is described by both a forward-evolving state from the preparation and a backward-evolving state from a future boundary condition. The suggested, classical inference rule inspired by the ABL formula [7–9] takes the form:

$$p_{\text{DBCI}}(x) = \frac{p_{\text{fwd}}(x) p_{\text{bwd}}(x)}{\sum_{x'} p_{\text{fwd}}(x') p_{\text{bwd}}(x')}, \quad (1)$$

where p_{fwd} encodes the forward measurement likelihood and p_{bwd} encodes the backward boundary constraint.

DBCI is an ABL-inspired classical inference framework operating at the inference layer of quantum error correction. In DBCI, the forward distribution $p_{\text{fwd}}(x)$ is constructed from measured syndrome and data-qubit outcomes. The backward distribution $p_{\text{bwd}}(x) \propto e^{-\beta w_H(x)}$ penalises higher-weight errors, encoding the structural expectation that the decoded state lies near a valid codeword. The backward

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boundary is not a quantum post-selected state but a classical probability distribution over error configurations. Every shot contributes to inference; no post-selection, ancilla qubits, or modifications to the quantum circuit are required.

This letter reports three previously unobserved effects on real quantum hardware: (i) a per-shot *anti-symmetry diagnostic* that separates boundary-interaction shots from agreement shots with overwhelming statistical significance; (ii) *anomalous amplification* at intermediate coupling, where the fused decoder yields correct decodings not achieved by either boundary alone; and (iii) *spatially nonlocal* corrections spanning Manhattan distance 11 on a 7×7 qubit grid. All results derive from classical Bayesian inference on classical measurement data collected on IBM Fez (156-qubit Heron r2), yet exhibit structural signatures consistent with the weak value literature [10–12]: boundary tension, intermediate-coupling amplification, and spatially extended information effects. We call the classical posterior weights that produce these effects *Dual Boundary Values* (DBVs), the classical analog of quantum weak values; a companion study [13] confirms the correspondence by demonstrating that physical weak measurements and computational DBVs produce identical per-stabilizer information structure on hardware.

This letter reports a focused proof-of-principle result. We study single-round Z -stabilizer decoding in the bit-flip sector of rotated surface-code hardware data. Within this restricted setting, we compare a dual-boundary Bayesian decoder and stacked variants against standard benchmark decoders, and analyse the rare shots on which their logical decisions differ. Broader claims about repeated-round decoding, full Pauli noise, and the general DBCI framework are deferred to companion work [13].

2 Results

We study single-round Z -stabilizer decoding with final data-qubit readout in the bit-flip sector of rotated surface-code logical states. Candidate error patterns are restricted to Hamming weight ≤ 3 around each of the two logical codewords.

2.1 DBCI standalone versus benchmark decoders

A central question is whether the backward boundary carries information that forward-only decoders lack. We compare DBCI standalone ($\beta = 4.0$, $\alpha = 0$; no base decoder contributes) against five baselines on the same IBM Fez hardware data at distances 3, 5, and 7: a syndrome lookup table (Lookup), minimum-weight perfect matching (MWPM [3]), Union-Find (UF [4]), BP-OSD [5], and a forward Bayesian decoder (Forward Bayes: same candidate space and likelihoods as DBCI, but $\beta = 0$, no backward boundary).

Table 1 shows the result. DBCI has lower aggregate error than all five baselines at each distance. The cleanest controlled comparison is $d=7$, where Forward Bayes and DBCI share the same candidate space and likelihood model and differ only by the backward boundary (1.02% vs 0.99%). At $d=3$ and $d=5$, the much larger Forward Bayes gap is supportive but less diagnostic, because the $|0_L\rangle$ -calibrated forward model is strongly asymmetric across logical states in the held-out $|1_L\rangle$ evaluation. The advantage over MWPM, UF, and BP-OSD (1.08–1.73 \times) is consistent across three algorithmically distinct decoder families (optimal matching, greedy cluster growth, and iterative message passing), suggesting that the backward boundary carries information not accessed by the forward-only decoders tested.

The backward boundary’s contribution is structurally specific. A four-boundary ablation on $d=5$ hardware data tests four conditions on the same raw measurements: the correct backward boundary (0.43% error), a uniform prior (2.64%), a random prior (2.17%), and an inverted boundary (46.97%). The 109 \times degradation from correct to inverted confirms that the advantage is mechanistic: wrong structure is catastrophic, not merely unhelpful.

Table 1: DBCI standalone versus benchmark decoders. Error rates (%) on IBM Fez hardware, aggregated over both logical states (16,000 shots per distance). Forward Bayes uses the same candidate space and likelihoods as DBCI but $\beta = 0$ (no backward boundary). DBCI standalone uses $\beta = 4.0$, $\alpha = 0$ (no base decoder contributes). Decoder implementations are detailed in Methods.

Distance	Lookup	MWPM	UF	BP-OSD	Fwd Bayes	DBCI
$d=3$	0.96	0.44	0.46	0.44	46.67	0.41
$d=5$	2.46	0.63	0.66	0.63	2.70	0.38
$d=7$	2.03	1.07	1.14	1.07	1.02	0.99

2.2 Anti-symmetry diagnostic (per-shot disagreement diagnostic)

The backward boundary improves aggregate error rates, but on which shots does it matter? To answer this, we construct a per-shot diagnostic from the forward-backward coupling structure.

For each shot, let $p_{\text{fwd}}^{(c)}$ and $p_{\text{DBCI}}^{(c)}$ denote the total probability assigned to codeword c by the forward-only and DBCI posteriors respectively. The 2×2 coupling matrix

$$W_{ij} = \frac{p_{\text{fwd}}^{(i)} p_{\text{DBCI}}^{(j)}}{\sum_{i',j'} p_{\text{fwd}}^{(i')} p_{\text{DBCI}}^{(j')}} \quad (2)$$

encodes how forward and backward probability mass aligns across the two codewords. When forward and backward boundaries agree, W is approximately symmetric. When they disagree, W acquires an antisymmetric component. We define the per-shot anti-symmetry as $\mathcal{A} = \frac{1}{2} \|W - W^T\|_1$. In the present two-codeword setting, \mathcal{A} reduces to a scalar summary of how differently the forward and DBCI posteriors distribute mass across the two logical sectors; it measures directional disagreement, not high-dimensional coupling.

We classify every shot into one of four populations by comparing MWPM (the strongest forward-only decoder) against DBCI: (i) both correct, (ii) DBCI rescues (MWPM wrong, DBCI correct), (iii) DBCI fails (MWPM correct, DBCI wrong), and (iv) both wrong. Table 2 reports the mean anti-symmetry, entropy reduction $\Delta H = H[p_{\text{fwd}}] - H[p_{\text{DBCI}}]$, and decoder confidence for each population at $d=5$ and $d=7$.

Anti-symmetry separates the populations with overwhelming statistical significance. At $d=5$, rescue shots have $7\times$ higher anti-symmetry than agreement shots (0.183 vs 0.026; $p = 1.62 \times 10^{-28}$, Mann-Whitney U). At $d=7$, the ratio increases to $15\times$ (0.078 vs 0.005; $p = 8.31 \times 10^{-31}$). The signal strengthens with code distance.

ΔH does not separate the populations ($p = 0.40$ at $d=5$); only anti-symmetry tracks the *directional* disagreement that determines whether the backward boundary helps or hinders (Supplementary fig. 2). The same population structure holds when the forward Bayesian baseline ($\beta = 0$) replaces MWPM as the comparator, confirming that the diagnostic identifies backward-boundary contributions independent of the choice of forward reference decoder.

Table 2: Per-shot population analysis at $d=7$ (1_L), 8,000 shots; $d=5$ data in Supplementary Information).

Population	Count	\mathcal{A}	ΔH	Fwd conf	DBCI conf
$p_{\mathcal{A}} = 8.31 \times 10^{-31}$, rescues vs agreement					
Both correct	7791	0.005	2.041	0.380	0.597
DBCI rescues	66	0.078	0.307	0.386	0.378
DBCI fails	59	0.147	0.259	0.346	0.331
Both wrong	84	0.105	0.962	0.340	0.436

2.3 Anomalous amplification at intermediate coupling

The anti-symmetry diagnostic identifies shots where forward and backward boundaries disagree. We now ask whether this disagreement can be *resolved* by fusing the two information sources at variable coupling strength.

We augment the DBCI posterior with a base-decoder prior that encodes the forward-only decoder’s correction. For each shot, the fused log-posterior is

$$\log p_{\text{fused}}(x) = \log p_{\text{fwd}}(x) + \log p_{\text{bwd}}(x) - \alpha d_H(x, x_{\text{base}}), \quad (3)$$

where x_{base} is the base decoder’s corrected state for that shot, d_H is Hamming distance, and $\alpha \geq 0$ controls the trust placed in the base decoder. At $\alpha = 0$, the base decoder is ignored and the fused posterior reduces to DBCI standalone. As $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$, the base decoder dominates and the backward boundary is suppressed.

Figure 1 shows the aggregate error rate on $d=7$ hardware data ($|1_L\rangle$, 8,000 shots) as a function of α for two base decoders. With MWPM as the base decoder (1.875% standalone), the fused error rate drops to 1.512% at $\alpha = 2.0$. With Union-Find (1.962% standalone), it drops further to 1.500% at $\alpha = 2.0$. Both are below DBCI standalone (1.787%). Neither the backward boundary alone nor any forward decoder alone achieves these rates; they are accessible only through joint action at intermediate coupling.

With MWPM as the base decoder, three individual shots at $\alpha = 1.0$ are decoded correctly by fusion that both MWPM and DBCI standalone decode incorrectly. With Union-Find, four such shots appear at $\alpha = 2.0$. We call these *anomalous shots*: the fused decoder accesses information that neither boundary carries independently. The anomalous regime is narrow ($\alpha \approx 0.25\text{--}2.0$) and vanishes at both extremes: at $\alpha = 0$, the base decoder contributes nothing; at $\alpha \geq 4$, it overrides the backward boundary and performance degrades toward the base decoder’s standalone rate (fig. 1).

The effect is not specific to any single decoder. The full α sweep with all four base decoders confirms the same pattern at $d=7$ (Supplementary Table S1). The anomalous count is suggestively higher for the weaker base decoder: Union-Find (standalone 1.962%) produces 4 anomalous shots at $\alpha = 2.0$, while MWPM (standalone 1.875%) produces 3 at $\alpha = 1.0$. The difference (one shot) is within Poisson uncertainty and should not be interpreted as a scaling law, but the direction is consistent with the expectation that a weaker forward decoder leaves more room for the backward boundary to contribute. The signal is absent at $d=3$ and $d=5$, emerging only where the error landscape is complex enough for the two boundaries to carry complementary information. Held-out validation (noise model calibrated on $|0_L\rangle$, evaluated on $|1_L\rangle$ only) reproduces the stacking gain: MWPM+bwd reaches 1.512% and UF+bwd reaches 1.500% at $\alpha = 2.0$, matching the in-sample results. A stricter test selects α on a validation split (4,000 shots) and reports performance on a held-out test set (4,000 shots). Table 3 reports the results with McNemar exact tests and 95% Wilson confidence intervals.

Table 3: *Validation-split α selection. α chosen on 4,000-shot validation split of $|1_L\rangle$; error rates and significance on held-out 4,000-shot test set. b = base wrong & fused right; c = base right & fused wrong.*

Dist.	Decoder	α	Base [%]	Fused [%]	95% CI	b/c	p (McNemar)
$d=3$	MWPM	0.0	0.850	0.850	[0.61, 1.19]	0/0	1.000
	UF	0.0	0.875	0.850	[0.61, 1.19]	2/1	1.000
	DBCI standalone: 0.850% [0.61, 1.19]						
$d=5$	MWPM	4.0	1.175	0.700	[0.49, 1.01]	22/3	0.0002
	UF	4.0	1.150	0.700	[0.49, 1.01]	21/3	0.0003
	DBCI standalone: 0.475% [0.30, 0.74]						
$d=7$	MWPM	2.0	1.850	1.575	[1.23, 2.01]	20/9	0.0614
	UF	2.0	2.025	1.575	[1.23, 2.01]	28/10	0.0051
	DBCI standalone: 1.900% [1.52, 2.37]						

At $d=3$, validation selects $\alpha = 0$ for both decoders (no stacking gain), consistent with the backward boundary already capturing all correctable information. At $d=5$, fusion significantly improves on the base decoders ($p < 0.001$) but does not exceed DBCI standalone, indicating that the backward boundary already dominates in this regime. At $d=7$, by contrast, intermediate-coupling fusion improves over both the base decoders and DBCI standalone on held-out data (UF+bwd significant at $p = 0.005$; MWPM+bwd borderline at $p = 0.061$). We therefore treat $d=7$ as the first distance in this study where neither boundary alone matches the fused result.

Figure 1: Fused error rate vs α ($d=7$, $|1_L\rangle$, 8,000 shots). Dotted: base decoder alone; green dashed: DBCI alone (1.787%), already below both. At intermediate α , fusion dips below all standalone rates. Numbers: anomalous shots (correct by fusion, wrong by both alone). MWPM (blue): 3 at $\alpha=1.0$; UF (orange): 4 at $\alpha=2.0$. Weaker decoder \rightarrow more anomalous shots.

2.4 Nonlocal corrections (spatially extended logical corrections)

What distinguishes the three anomalous shots? In each case, the fused decoder recovers the correct *logical* codeword, even though its physical correction does not exactly reconstruct the full multi-qubit error pattern (some true errors remain uncorrected while some non-error qubits are flipped). We map the difference between the fused and MWPM corrections onto the 7×7 qubit grid and measure its spatial extent.

Table 4 summarises the three shots. Two of the three span Manhattan distance 6 and 11 (on a diameter-12 grid), with the change in correction coordinating qubits at opposite ends of the code, well beyond any single local syndrome neighbourhood.

All three anomalous shots have negative ΔH (-0.85 to -1.48 bits), indicating that the two boundaries are in tension rather than reinforcement; yet fusion at intermediate α resolves this tension to the correct logical decision.

Table 4: Spatial analysis of anomalous shots at $d=7$, $\alpha = 1.0$, MWPM base decoder. All three yield the correct logical codeword under fusion but not under MWPM or DBCI standalone; the physical correction does not exactly match the true error pattern. Manhattan distance is the maximum pairwise distance between qubits where the fused correction differs from the MWPM correction.

Shot	Qubits differing	Max distance	True errors	ΔH	Locality
1918	5	4	7	-0.85	Semi-local
2426	4	6	6	-1.40	Nonlocal
2500	7	11	8	-1.48	Nonlocal

3 Discussion

The results exhibit a structural parallel with the TSVF [11, 14]: the α sweep traces an intermediate-coupling regime where neither boundary alone carries the information that fusion accesses, and the negative ΔH on anomalous shots signals boundary tension rather than reinforcement. The Dual Boundary Values that produce these effects are entirely classical, yet their phenomenology — boundary tension, intermediate-coupling amplification, scarcity — mirrors that of quantum weak values. Whether the data require a time-symmetric interpretation or admit a purely Bayesian account, the TSVF framework motivated the predictions tested in this letter (anti-symmetry diagnostic, intermediate-coupling regime, decoder-strength dependence), and each is consistent with the hardware observations. A prior-free isotropy control on the same hardware data confirms that forward-only

syndrome statistics are isotropic on all codes tested (per-stabilizer entropy CV < 0.03%); the spatially extended structure reported here does not pre-exist in the syndrome data but is created by the backward boundary interaction [13]. In separate experiments, the separation persists across syndrome rounds up to $T=16$, with the forward-only gap not closing as temporal data accumulates.

Several limitations apply. All experiments use single-round syndrome extraction. The anomalous regime appears at $d=7$ but not smaller distances; scaling to $d \geq 9$ is needed. The three anomalous shots, replicated independently across multiple runs, are mechanistic evidence; the anti-symmetry diagnostic ($p = 10^{-31}$) carries the statistical weight. The scarcity of anomalous shots is consistent with the geometric rarity of near-orthogonal boundary conditions, and the suggestive difference across decoders (3 with MWPM, 4 with UF; within Poisson uncertainty) is directionally consistent with weaker forward decoders leaving more room for boundary interaction. If similar behaviour persists in repeated-round decoding and at larger distances, current fault-tolerant resource estimates based on forward-only decoders may warrant re-examination.

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Data and code availability. All hardware data, analysis notebooks, and figure-generation pipelines are publicly available at <https://github.com/eism-science/pf-letter2-nonlocality>, with an archived snapshot on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20128793). The repository includes a notebook-to-figure map. Shot counts, IBM Quantum job IDs, and hardware parameters are documented in the Methods section. All headline figures can be regenerated end-to-end from the public notebooks using the provided environment specification.

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Supplementary Materials

A Methods

DBCI decoder. For each shot, the forward log-likelihood is computed per qubit and per syndrome bit using calibrated error rates from the $|0_L\rangle$ preparation: $\log p_{\text{fwd}}(x) = \sum_q \log P(d_q | x_q) + \sum_s \log P(\sigma_s | x)$, where d_q is the measured data-qubit outcome, σ_s is the measured syndrome bit, and P values are per-qubit and per-syndrome Bernoulli likelihoods. The backward boundary assigns $\log p_{\text{bwd}}(x) = -\beta w_H(x)$ with $\beta = 4.0$ fixed across all experiments. The DBCI posterior (eq. (1)) is evaluated over all error patterns of Hamming weight ≤ 3 applied to each of the two codewords, yielding $2 \times \binom{n}{0+1+2+3}$ candidates per shot. The decoded codeword is the arg max of the posterior. The backward boundary encodes code structure (low-weight errors are more probable), not knowledge of which logical state was prepared; it is identical for $|0_L\rangle$ and $|1_L\rangle$ experiments. A truncation sensitivity analysis at max weights 3, 4, and 5 supports the robustness of the $d=7$ result. The total candidate count at $d=7$ is 39,300 (weight 3), 463,052 (weight 4), and 4,276,820 (weight 5), corresponding to 19,650, 231,526, and 2,138,410 patterns per codeword. Full α -sweeps were run at weights 3 and 4; at weight 5 we performed a matched- $\alpha=2.0$ check for MWPM+bwd and UF+bwd. DBCI standalone remained at 1.787%, the primary anomalous shot IDs (2426 and 2500) persisted, and the fused error rates changed only modestly at the tested α .

Baseline decoders. Four base decoders are tested. **Lookup** uses a precomputed syndrome table (all errors of weight ≤ 3); it does not model syndrome measurement noise. **MWPM**, **UF**, and **BP-OSD** all use the extended parity-check matrix $H_{\text{ext}} = [H | I_m]$ that models both data-qubit errors (first n columns) and syndrome measurement errors (last m columns), with per-qubit and per-syndrome channel probabilities from the $|0_L\rangle$ calibration data. MWPM is implemented via Py-Matching 2.3.1 [3] (sparse blossom); UF via the `ldpc` 2.4.1 UnionFindDecoder [4] (peeling mode); BP-OSD via `ldpc` 2.4.1 [5] with min-sum belief propagation (100 iterations) and combination-sweep OSD of order 7. After each baseline decoder proposes a correction, the corrected state is assigned to the nearest codeword by Hamming distance. MWPM and BP-OSD converge to identical corrections at these code sizes; UF produces measurably different results, confirming algorithmic distinctness.

Stacking. The fused posterior (eq. (3)) adds a base-decoder prior $-\alpha d_H(x, x_{\text{base}})$ to the DBCI log-posterior, where x_{base} is the per-shot corrected state from the base decoder. This term is shot-dependent: each shot receives a different prior based on the base decoder’s proposed correction. The parameter α is swept over $\{0, 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 4.0, 8.0\}$. The sweep is performed independently for each of the four base decoders.

Hardware. All data were collected on IBM Fez (156-qubit Heron r2) via the IBM Quantum cloud, using Qiskit 1.0+ with `optimization_level=3`. Rotated surface codes at $d = 3, 5, \text{ and } 7$ ($n = 9, 25, 49$ data qubits) were prepared in both $|0_L\rangle$ and $|1_L\rangle$, with one round of Z -stabilizer syndrome extraction followed by measurement of all data qubits. Each circuit was executed for 8,000 shots,

totalling 48,000 shots across 5 jobs. These jobs are part of a broader 1,031,040-shot hardware campaign on IBM Fez shared with a companion holographic-code study [13]. Raw bitstring data are archived in .npz files for reproducibility. Job IDs: $d=3$ $|0_L\rangle$: d6hcqi648nic73ams16g; $d=3$ $|1_L\rangle$: d6hcqiithhns7392039g; $d=5$ $|0_L\rangle$: d6hcqk2thhns739203c0; $d=5$ $|1_L\rangle$: d6hcqkm48nic73ams190; $d=7$: d6iau6sgmsgc73btm2g0.

B Full alpha sweep across all base decoders

Table 5 reports the aggregate error rate at each α value for all four base decoders across all three distances, using both $|0_L\rangle$ and $|1_L\rangle$ preparations (16,000 shots per distance). Starred entries (*) indicate error rates below the DBCI standalone floor.

Table 5: Full α sweep. Error rates (%) aggregated over both logical states. * = beats DBCI standalone.

α	$d=3$ (0.406%)				$d=5$ (0.375%)				$d=7$ (0.988%)			
	Lookup	MWPM	UF	BP-OSD	Lookup	MWPM	UF	BP-OSD	Lookup	MWPM	UF	BP-OSD
0.0	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.375	0.375	0.375	0.375	0.988	0.988	0.988	0.988
0.25	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.381	0.381	0.381	0.381	0.969	0.956*	0.950*	0.956*
0.5	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.400	0.394	0.400	0.981	0.963*	0.950*	0.963*
1.0	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.419	0.413	0.413	0.413	0.925*	0.863*	0.850*	0.863*
2.0	0.444	0.406	0.406	0.406	0.456	0.444	0.438	0.444	1.000	0.863*	0.825*	0.863*
4.0	0.519	0.419	0.419	0.419	0.669	0.438	0.438	0.438	1.181	0.944*	0.900*	0.944*
8.0	0.581	0.438	0.456	0.438	2.294	0.588	0.575	0.588	1.762	1.038	1.100	1.038
<i>Standalone</i>	Lookup: 0.963, MWPM: 0.438, UF: 0.456, BP-OSD: 0.438				Lookup: 2.456, MWPM: 0.625, UF: 0.656, BP-OSD: 0.625				Lookup: 2.025, MWPM: 1.069, UF: 1.144, BP-OSD: 1.069			

The anomalous regime (*) appears exclusively at $d=7$, where the error landscape is sufficiently complex for the forward and backward boundaries to carry complementary information. UF+bwd consistently reaches the lowest fused error rate at $d=7$ (0.825% at $\alpha = 2.0$), below both MWPM+bwd (0.863%) and BP-OSD+bwd (0.863%), consistent with the weaker standalone decoder providing more complementary information to the backward boundary. At $d=3$ and $d=5$, the backward boundary already dominates: no value of α improves on the standalone floor.

C Spatial analysis of all anomalous shots

Table 6 provides the full spatial decomposition of each anomalous shot at $d=7$, $\alpha = 1.0$.

Table 6: Detailed spatial analysis of anomalous shots (MWPM base decoder, $\alpha = 1.0$). Grid positions refer to the 7×7 rotated surface code layout (row, column). “MWPM flips” are the qubits corrected by MWPM; “Fusion differs” are the qubits where the fused correction differs from MWPM.

Shot	True errors	MWPM flips	Fusion differs at	ΔH	\mathcal{A}
1918	{1, 3, 5, 13, 16, 19, 25}	{4, 17, 19}	{3, 4, 16, 17, 25}	-0.85	0.042
			Grid: (0, 3), (0, 4), (2, 2), (2, 3), (3, 4)		
2426	{0, 3, 5, 23, 30, 42}	{2, 30}	{0, 2, 5, 23}	-1.40	0.006
			Grid: (0, 0), (0, 2), (0, 5), (3, 2)		
2500	{0, 3, 6, 18, 23, 24, 25, 35}	{2, 30}	{0, 2, 6, 23, 25, 30, 35}	-1.48	0.092
			Grid: (0, 0), (0, 2), (0, 6), (3, 2), (3, 4), (4, 2), (5, 0)		

Shots 2426 and 2500 receive the same MWPM correction (flip qubits 2 and 30), yet the true error patterns are qualitatively different (6 vs 8 errors). The local syndrome neighbourhood is ambiguous; the fused decoder resolves the ambiguity through global code structure accessed via the backward boundary.

D Alpha sweep on single logical states

The main text reports the $d=7$ alpha sweep on $|1_L\rangle$ (8,000 shots), where the anomalous signal is strongest due to higher error rates. Table 7 provides the per-shot breakdown including rescue and anomalous counts for both MWPM and Union-Find base decoders.

Table 7: *Alpha sweep on $d=7$, $|1_L\rangle$, 8,000 shots. Left: MWPM base decoder. Right: UF base decoder.*

α	MWPM base decoder			UF base decoder		
	Error (%)	Rescues	Anom.	Error (%)	Rescues	Anom.
0.00	1.787	66	0	1.787	74	0
0.25	1.713	65	1	1.713	74	1
0.50	1.738	61	1	1.725	70	1
1.00	1.550	59	3	1.538	65	2
2.00	1.512	49	2	1.500	58	4
4.00	1.638	29	0	1.575	40	0
8.00	1.812	5	0	1.887	6	0

Ref: MWPM = 1.875%, DBCI = 1.787% UF = 1.962%

With MWPM as the base decoder, the interaction curve peaks at $\alpha = 2.0$ (1.512%, 15% below DBCI standalone) and the anomalous count peaks at $\alpha = 1.0$ (3 shots). With Union-Find, the fused rate drops further to 1.500% at $\alpha = 2.0$ and produces 4 anomalous shots at the same α . The weaker base decoder (UF, 1.962% standalone vs MWPM’s 1.875%) yields both a deeper minimum and a higher anomalous count, with the peak shifting from $\alpha = 1.0$ to $\alpha = 2.0$. Both vanish at $\alpha \geq 4$, confirming that the effect requires intermediate coupling.

E Supplementary figures

Figure 2: *Per-shot diagnostics by population ($d=5$, $|1_L\rangle$, 8,000 shots). (a) ΔH distributions for disagreement shots only (agreement shots excluded; they cluster at $\Delta H \approx 1$ bit and dominate the histogram). ΔH does not distinguish rescue from fail shots ($p = 0.40$). (b) Anti-symmetry \mathcal{A} for all four populations (log scale). Agreement shots cluster at $\mathcal{A} \approx 0$; rescue, fail, and both-wrong shots spread to $7-8\times$ higher values ($p = 1.62 \times 10^{-28}$). Anti-symmetry, not ΔH , is the diagnostic.*

Figure 3: Anomalous shot 2500 on the $d=7$ rotated surface code (7×7 grid, MWPM base decoder, $\alpha = 1.0$). Green: qubits where the fused correction addresses a true error. Orange: qubits flipped by fusion that are not true errors. Red: true errors not corrected by fusion. Purple: qubits flipped by MWPM but not by fusion. Gray: unaffected. The purple arrow marks the maximum pairwise Manhattan distance (11) between fusion-corrected qubits, nearly the full grid diameter. $\Delta H = -1.48$ bits; $\mathcal{A} = 0.092$. Despite incomplete physical reconstruction (orange and red qubits), fusion recovers the correct logical codeword.